

Impact of granular activated carbon, voltage application and sewage sludge pretreatment on mesophilic anaerobic digestion performance and per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances removal

Evdokia Gkalipidou^a, Michalis Deligiannis^a, Georgia Gatidou^a, Emma R. Knight^b, Ian J. Allan^b, Marios G. Kostakis^c, Dimitrios Triantafyllos Gerokonstantis^c, Olga S. Arvaniti^d, Nikolaos S. Thomaidis^c, Ioannis Vyrides^e, Michail S. Fountoulakis^{a,f,*}, Athanasios S. Stasinakis^a

^a Department of Environment, University of the Aegean, Mytilene 81100, Greece

^b Norwegian Institute for Water Research (NIVA), Økernveien 94, Oslo 0579, Norway

^c Department of Chemistry, National and Kapodistrian University of Athens, Athens 15771, Greece

^d Department of Agricultural Development, Agrofood and Management of Natural Resources, National and Kapodistrian University of Athens, Psachna 34400, Greece

^e Department of Chemical Engineering, Cyprus University of Technology, 95 Eirinis Str., Limassol 3603, Cyprus

^f School of Chemical and Environmental Engineering, Technical University of Crete, Chania 73100, Greece

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ABSTRACT

Four laboratory-scale mesophilic anaerobic digesters were operated in parallel to investigate the impact of granular activated carbon (GAC) addition, voltage application, and thermal and ultrasound pretreatment on anaerobic digestion (AD) performance, as well as the distribution and removal of seven per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS). When raw sludge was used as feed, there were no statistically significant differences in volatile solids (VS) and soluble chemical oxygen demand (sCOD) removal, biogas yield or methane content between the reactors. Ultrasound or thermal sludge pretreatment increased the solubilisation of organic compounds but did not enhance methane production. The highest sCOD and VS removal ($79 \pm 11\%$ and $52 \pm 17\%$, respectively) was observed in bioreactors containing GAC after sludge thermal pretreatment. The addition of GAC into biochemical methane potential tests accelerated the consumption of VFAs and enhanced maximum methane production. PFAS distribution analysis showed that an increase of perfluorocarbon chain length and the presence of a sulfonic acid group reduced the fraction of PFAS found in the dissolved phase. Thermal and ultrasound pretreatment of sludge slightly increased the fraction of longer perfluorocarboxylic acids and perfluorooctane sulfonic acid in the dissolved phase, without affecting the total concentrations of PFAS in the pretreated sludge or digestate. Batch and continuous-flow experiments demonstrated significant total PFAS removal in bioreactors containing GAC, suggesting possible biotransformation, while the application of voltage did not affect their concentrations. Genera found in higher abundance in GAC systems, but not in systems without GAC, included *Deftuviococcus*, *Limnobacter*, *Romboutsia* and *Methanomethylovorans*.

1. Introduction

Anaerobic digestion (AD) is a well-established and commonly applied technology for the stabilization of sewage sludge and the production of biogas [1]. To improve the performance of anaerobic digesters, several modifications of the process have been tested to enhance the potential for electron transfer between anaerobic microorganisms

[2]. Among these, the addition of conductive materials which act as 'electric connection bridges' appear to potentially enhance AD efficiency by promoting direct interspecies electron transfer (DIET), providing a large surface area for microbial community growth, maintaining pH stability and adsorbing toxic compounds [3]. To date, several carbon-based conductive materials such as activated carbon, graphite, carbon cloth and their combinations, have been tested [4,5].

* Corresponding author at: School of Chemical and Environmental Engineering, Technical University of Crete, Chania 73100, Greece.

E-mail addresses: fountoulakis@tuc.gr, fountoulakis@env.aegean.gr (M.S. Fountoulakis).

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Additionally, DIET can be achieved through the application of electrical voltage (EV), and the combination of EV and conductive materials could potentially be more effective in enhancing AD [6].

Another approach aimed at enhancing AD performance involves the application of mechanical, chemical, biological, or physical pretreatment of sewage sludge, which leads to the disruption of complex microbial sludge cells and improves the hydrolysis step [7–9]. Among the different pretreatment processes, the most commonly applied method for pretreating sludge is thermal [10], split into low-temperature (LTTP, < 100 °C) and high-temperature (HTTP, > 100 °C) thermal pretreatment. Although most full-scale systems operate under high HTTP conditions, several studies have shown that LLTP can boost biogas production often providing better energy efficiency than HTTP [11]. Additionally, LTTP helps prevent high ammonia levels and the formation of recalcitrant compounds, such as melanoidins, which are commonly observed using HTTP [12]. On the other hand, ultrasonication is a mechanical sludge pretreatment method in which cell disintegration and the breakdown of complex organic compounds are achieved by cavitation phenomena [13]. The efficiency of the process is affected by various parameters such as volume and sludge characteristics, power input, power density and duration of the ultrasound treatment [14]. Some of the positive outcomes of the sonication pretreatment include improved removal of VS [15], enhanced adsorption efficiency of harmful substances by adsorbents [16] and a reduction in sludge viscosity [17].

Since 2000, the presence of organic micropollutants in wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) and their fate during sludge treatment has received increased attention [18,19]. Among organic micropollutants, per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS) are widely used in everyday and industrial products and are frequently detected in sewage sludge at concentrations in the range of $\mu\text{g/g}$ [20,21]. Chemical properties such as high polarity and strong carbon-fluorine bonds make them highly persistent and difficult to biodegrade in environmental matrices [22]. Even though PFAS are commonly detected in sewage sludge, the number of studies examining their fate and removal during sludge AD are limited. In a recent article examining the removal of PFAS in Canadian full-scale anaerobic digesters, Lakshminarasimman et al. [23], observed a moderate decrease for the sum of 13 studied PFAS ($\Sigma\text{PFAS-F}$ removal: 10–38 %) in three out of five anaerobic digesters. In another study by Alukkal et al. [24], a 32 % reduction in the total concentration of 58 studied PFAS from a full-scale sludge system combining thermal hydrolysis pretreatment (CAMBI® B6-4, 165 °C, 6 bar) with AD was observed. Recent anaerobic laboratory experiments have reported the defluorination of perfluorooctane sulfonic acid (PFOS) and perfluorooctanoic acid (PFOA) using pure and enriched cultures of *Acidimicrobium* sp. strain A6 [25], microbial reductive defluorination of two branched unsaturated per- and polyfluorinated carboxylic acids with dehalorespiring cultures [26] and the decrease of concentrations of PFOS with simultaneous production of fluorine during anaerobic digestion of a glucose-based synthetic medium [27]. Recently, Deligiannis et al. [28] observed a partial decrease in the total concentration of certain PFAS in thermophilic anaerobic digesters containing granular activated carbon (GAC) as conductive material, along with an increase in the abundance of specific microorganisms, such as *Acinetobacter* and *Pseudomonas*. Limited information is currently available on the fate and removal of PFAS under mesophilic sewage sludge anaerobic digestion when GAC is added as a conductive material or when voltage is applied. To the best of our knowledge, no data also exist on the potential role of thermal or ultrasound sludge pretreatment in the removal of PFAS during sludge anaerobic digestion.

The main objectives of this article were to study the performance of the mesophilic AD process modified by the application of GAC, voltage and sludge pretreatment, and to examine the fate of selected PFAS, including perfluoropentanoic acid (PFPeA), perfluoroheptanoic acid (PFHpA), PFOA, perfluorononanoic acid (PFNA), perfluorodecanoic acid (PFDA), perfluoroundecanoic acid (PFUdA) and linear and total

PFOS in these bioreactors. Three experimental phases were conducted using raw sewage sludge (Phase A), thermally pretreated sludge (Phase B) and ultrasound pretreated sludge (Phase C) over a period of five months. Four laboratory-scale strictly anaerobic reactors operated in parallel and in continuous mode during each Phase. The first reactor operated as a conventional anaerobic digester while GAC, voltage and a combination of GAC with voltage were applied to the other three, respectively. All reactors were systematically monitored for the removal of volatile solids (VS), the production of biogas and volatile fatty acids (VFAs) while the concentrations of PFAS were determined both in the dissolved and the particulate phase. The composition of biomass was also investigated by applying 16S rRNA gene sequencing. Batch experiments were also carried out to investigate the potential effect of GAC addition on target PFAS removal.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Analytical standards and reagents

All native PFAS standards (PFPeA, PFHpA, PFOA, PFNA, PFDA, PFUdA, PFOS) were purchased by Alfa Aesar (Germany) while mass-labelled standards of $^{13}\text{C}_5$ -perfluorohexanoic acid (PFHxA), $^{13}\text{C}_8$ -PFOA, $^{13}\text{C}_9$ -PFNA, $^{13}\text{C}_6$ -PFDA, $^{13}\text{C}_7$ -PFUnDA, $^{13}\text{C}_3$ -perfluorohexane sulfonic acid, and $^{13}\text{C}_8$ -PFOS that were used as internal standards or surrogate standards, were supplied by Wellington Laboratories (Canada). Stock solutions of native standards were initially prepared in methanol (MeOH) at concentrations of 1000 mg/L from which a mixture of target compounds was made (160 mg/L) and stored at $-18\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. Liquid chromatography mass spectrometry (LC-MS) grade MeOH and acetonitrile (ACN) were supplied by Merck (Germany). Oasis solid phase extraction (SPE) HLB cartridges (200 mg, 6 mL) were supplied by WatersTM (Milford, MA, USA). Paper filters (5–13 μm) and syringe RC-filters (0.2 μm) were obtained by LLG (Germany) and Macherey-Nagel (Germany), respectively. Acetic acid (99.7 %) and ultra-pure HCl (32 %) were supplied by Merck (Germany), while ultra-pure water was produced in the laboratory by a Milli-Q[®] /Milli-RO Millipore system. GAC used in batch and continuous-flow experiments (Ravazol B-830, effective size: 0.8–1.0 mm, porosity = 0.4, apparent density = $475 \pm 25\text{ kg m}^{-3}$) was supplied by Inaqua (Germany) and was produced from bituminous coal by steam activation.

2.2. Batch anaerobic digestion experiments

Biochemical methane potential (BMP) tests were initially carried out to investigate the potential effect of GAC addition on target PFAS removal, based on the BMP protocol suggested by Angelidaki et al. [29]. For this purpose, four serum bottles, with a volume of 120 mL, were placed in a thermostatic water bath under mesophilic conditions (37 °C) and monitored for a period of 53 days. The working volume of the batch reactors was 80 mL, consisting of 40 mL of anaerobic digested sludge used as inoculum and 40 mL of sewage sludge mixture (20 mL primary sludge + 20 mL secondary sludge). The first pair of serum bottles represented the conventional AD process (AD), while in the second pair, GAC was added at a concentration of 10 g/L (AD + GAC). To maintain a stable pH during the experiment, 2.6 g/L of sodium bicarbonate (NaHCO_3) was added to each serum bottle while each studied PFAS was spiked at concentration of 50 $\mu\text{g/L}$. After filling, serum bottles were sealed with butyl rubber stoppers and aluminium crimps, and purged with nitrogen gas (N_2) for 1 min to remove oxygen from the headspace and maintain methanogenic conditions. Biogas was measured daily by the displacement of a piston of a gas-tight plastic syringe inserted into the serum bottles. Methane content was determined using gas chromatography (6890N, Agilent) equipped with a flame ionization detector (FID). At the start and at the end of the experiment, the total (sum of dissolved and particulate) concentration of target PFAS was measured. For this reason, samples were collected and oven dried in 60 °C until

constant weight and stored at $-18\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ before extraction and analysis.

2.3. Operation of continuous-flow mesophilic anaerobic digesters

To study the role of GAC addition and voltage application on the performance of anaerobic digestion four continuous-flow stirred-tank anaerobic digesters (working volume: 1 L) were operated for 162 days in parallel, under mesophilic conditions ($37\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$) and hydraulic retention time (HRT) of 20 days. This HRT was selected as it is commonly applied in lab-scale and full-scale mesophilic anaerobic digesters treating sewage sludge [19,30]. In Anaerobic Digester 1 (AD-V), an external voltage (electric potential: 2 V) was applied using a digital bench DC Power supply (QJ30005C, QJE) through carbon cloth electrodes ($4\text{ cm} \times 5\text{ cm}$), which were fully submerged into the sludge. In Anaerobic Digester 2 (AD-V-GAC), an external voltage (2 V) and GAC (10 g/L) were simultaneously applied. Anaerobic Digester 3 contained 10 g/L GAC (AD-GAC) while Anaerobic Digester 4 (AD) operated as a conventional anaerobic reactor with no addition of GAC and voltage (Table S1).

Three Experimental Phases (A–C) were conducted. For the start-up of the reactors, digested sludge was used from a mesophilic anaerobic digester treating agro-industrial wastewater [4]. The sludge feed was prepared daily by mixing 30 % primary and 70 % secondary sludge provided by WWTPs found in Lesvos Island (Greece). Following 30 days of acclimation to the substrate, a mixture of PFAS was spiked into the sludge to achieve an initial nominal concentration of $100\text{ }\mu\text{g/L}$ ($\approx 4\text{ }\mu\text{g/g}$ TS) for each target compound, and the systems were monitored for a period of 42 days (Experimental Phase A). This concentration was at the upper end of the range typically reported for PFOS in real-world sludge samples, and up to 10 times higher than those usually observed for other PFAS compounds [31]. To examine the effect of thermal pretreatment, thermally pretreated sludge ($80\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, 1 h) was used as feed during Experimental Phase B and the bioreactors operated under these conditions for 51 days. The thermal pretreatment of sludge (spiked with $100\text{ }\mu\text{g/L}$ of PFAS) was performed daily in a 1 L borosilicate reagent bottle, placed on a magnetic stirrer (SBS A-06) and the temperature monitored continuously with a digital thermometer that was set into the bottle. Time was recorded from the moment the homogeneous mixture reached the target temperature. To examine the effect of ultrasound pretreatment on AD, raw sludge (spiked with $100\text{ }\mu\text{g/L}$ of PFAS) was subjected daily to sonication at 320 W for 15 min with a frequency of 20 kHz using an Omni Sonic Ruptor 400 Ultrasonic Homogenizer. The power density applied was 1.12 W/mL and calculated according to Zhang et al. [32]. The duration of Experimental Phase C was 39 days.

To monitor the performance of the reactors, samples were taken twice a week from the influents and effluents for soluble chemical oxygen demand (sCOD), total solids (TS), VS and VFAs and once a week for PFASs (analysis both in the dissolved and particulate phase). The volume and the composition of produced biogas in each bioreactor were measured twice a week. Biogas was collected in gas bags attached to the gas outlet of each reactor [4]. Samples were also collected before and after pretreatment from Phases B and C to investigate whether thermal and ultrasound treatment had any effect on sludge characteristics and PFAS concentrations. To evaluate possible differences on the microbial profile of the digested sludge, samples were taken from the different bioreactors at the end of Phase A.

2.4. Analytical methods

Analyses of TS, VS and sCOD were conducted according to standard methods (APHA, 2005). For the sCOD, samples were centrifuged at 2500 rpm for 5 min, filtered (47 mm LLG-Filter papers, LLG-Labware, Germany), and analysed using the closed reflux colorimetric method. The determination of VFAs (acetic acid, propionic acid, butyric acid, isobutyric acid, valeric acid and isovaleric acid) was conducted using an Agilent 6890 N GC with a flame ionization detector, where a 0.001 mL of centrifuged, filtered and acidified sample ($10\text{ }\%$ H_3PO_4 to pH 1–2) was

directly injected into the inlet. The carrier gas used was helium and the run time for every sample analysis was 15 min. The detector and injector temperature were set at $250\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ [33].

To determine total (dissolved + particulate) PFAS concentration in BMP experiments, $0.1 \pm 0.02\text{ g}$ of dried material was weighed into a 15 mL centrifuge tube with an addition of mass-labelled internal standard mixture (Table S2), pretreated according to the method found in Section 1 of Supplementary material and analyzed using ultra performance liquid chromatography (Waters Acquity™ UPLC) coupled to a triple quadrupole time of flight (Waters Xevo® G2-S QTOF).

In continuous-flow experiments, PFASs were analyzed both in the dissolved and solid phase according to the method described by Arvaniti et al. [34] and Deligiannis et al. [28]. In brief, Oasis HLB SPE cartridges were used for the isolation of PFAS from the liquid samples while solid samples were extracted by ultra-sonication and cleaned up following the SPE method applied for liquid phase. An Exion UPLC system coupled to an AB Sciex QTRAP mass spectrometer 6500 + (AB Sciex, Canada) and was used for the qualitative and quantitative determination of target compounds. A detailed description of the analytical method can be found in Section 2 of Supplementary material.

2.5. High-throughput 16 S rRNA gene sequencing

At the end of the Phase A continuous-flow experiment the microbial profile in each bioreactor was analyzed to assess the microbial community composition, following the methodology described in Deligiannis et al. [28]. DNA was extracted from 250 mg of sludge using the DNeasy Power Soil Pro Kit (Qiagen, Germany) and sequenced at DNASense ApS (Denmark). Universal primers targeting the 16S rRNA gene (515FB and 1391 R) were used for PCR amplification under optimized conditions. Sequencing was conducted on a MinION platform with reads filtered and mapped to the MiDAS database (v4.8.1). Rigorous quality control measures ensured reliable identification of microbial operational taxonomic units, excluding low-abundance sequences ($< 0.01\text{ }\%$). Data analysis performed using R (v4.3.0) with specialized packages, provided a comprehensive insight into the microbial communities within the reactors.

2.6. Equations and statistical analysis

To assess the efficiency of the batch experiment setup, the Modified Gompertz equation was used by fitting raw data in the following manner (Eq. (1)):

$$CMP(t) = P_m \bullet \exp \left\{ - \exp \left[\frac{R_m \bullet e}{P_m} (\lambda - (t) + 1) \right] \right\} \quad (1)$$

where $CMP(t)$ is the cumulative methane production at time, t (mL), P_m is the maximum methane production (mL), R_m is the maximum methane production rate (potential for methane production) (mL/d), λ is the duration of lag phase (days) and e is Euler's constant (2.718).

The removal of PFAS in continuous-flow experiments was calculated using Eq. (2):

$$Removal(\%) = \frac{M_{in} - M_{out}}{M_{in}} \times 100 \quad (2)$$

where, M_{in} is the mass of each studied compound at the inlet and M_{out} is the mass of each studied compound at the outlet.

The PFAS masses (expressed as ng/d) were calculated by taking into account the PFAS found both in the dissolved and solid phase (Eq. (3)):

$$M = (C_{dis} \times Q) + (C_s \times TS \times Q) \quad (3)$$

where, Q is the sludge flowrate (L/d), C_{dis} is the concentration of PFAS in the dissolved phase (ng/L), C_s is the concentration of PFAS on the suspended solids (ng/mg) and TS is the concentration of the total

suspended solids (mg/L).

For BMP experiments, the model fit was carried out using OriginPro 2022 (Originlab, USA) software and the degree of fit was determined by the squared correlation coefficient (R^2). The same software was used for the construction of figures. To compare statistical differences between bioreactors on biogas production, VS and PFAS removal, one-way ANOVA was used and the Tukey's honestly significant difference (HSD) post hoc test was run when ANOVA was significant at $p < 0.05$.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Batch anaerobic digestion experiment

The BMP tests with added GAC exhibited higher maximum methane production (P_m) values compared with those of conventional AD (Table S3). The average values of P_m were 205 ± 3.4 mL for the conventional AD and 261 ± 3.7 mL for the serum bottles supplemented with 10 g/L GAC. The corresponding biogas yields were 371 and 498 mL biogas/g VS sludge added, while the methane yields were 237 and 302 mL methane/g VS sludge added, respectively. The values of the correlation factor (R^2) showed that the experimental data fitted well to the Modified Gompertz equation (0.96 and 0.98) while the lag phase (λ) was < 0.1 for both examined conditions. In a previous study, Altamirano-Corona et al. [35] examined the effect of GAC, biochar and magnetite on food waste AD and reported negative lag period in reactors where 10 g/L GAC had been added indicating prompt nutrient uptake. It is possible that activated carbon accelerates the biodegradation of VFAs which leads to a shorter start-up period of AD [36]. Analysis of six VFAs (expressed as COD-VFAs, mg/L) at the end of the BMP experiments showed that no VFAs were detected in the two reactors containing GAC. This indicates that the addition of this conductive material facilitated VFAs degradation. On the other hand, in the absence of GAC, four VFAs were detected, namely acetic acid (80 mg/L), propionic acid (853 mg/L), isobutyric acid (229 mg/L) and butyric acid (491 mg/L). Another study found a similar result, where the presence of GAC and trace elements (TEs) for the AD of food waste found that accumulation of VFAs was restricted and favoured DIET [37]. Similarly, Fountoulakis et al. [38] reported that incorporating GAC into BMP tests for dairy wastewater treatment accelerates the consumption of VFAs and COD compared to conventional AD. They concluded that the likely mechanism for VFAs reduction in GAC-amended reactors involves sorption onto the GAC surface, followed by their biotransformation into methane.

Determination of the total concentration of each PFAS in the samples collected at the start and at the end of the experiment showed that the addition of GAC led to significant removal of each PFAS during the experiment (Fig. 1). Specifically, the removal in these reactors ranged

Fig. 1. Total PFAS removal (%) in biomethane potential (BMP) experiments ($n = 2$).

between 68 % (PFPeA) and 79 % (PFNA) while in the BMP tests containing no GAC (conventional AD), the removal of PFAS did not exceed 31 %. To further study the performance of mesophilic AD using GAC as a conductive material and to examine the distribution and removal of target PFAS, continuous experiments were conducted.

3.2. Performance of continuous-flow mesophilic anaerobic experiments

The values of pH, TS and VS in the influents and effluents of the bioreactors in Experimental Phases A–C, as well as the removal of VS and sCOD, and the production of biogas and methane, are presented in Table S4.

In Experimental Phase A, the average pH values in the effluents of each reactor ranged between 6.98 ± 0.12 (AD-V) and 7.11 ± 0.13 (AD), while the concentration of TS ranged between 23.1 ± 3.9 mg/L for reactor AD and 29.7 ± 5.1 mg/L for AD-V-GAC (Table S4). The average VS removal ranged between 20 ± 7 % (AD-V) and 32 ± 12 % (AD-GAC) while the removal of sCOD between 43 ± 21 % (AD) and 51 ± 19 % (AD-V). Slightly higher mean daily biogas yield was observed in AD-GAC and AD bioreactors (292 ± 90 mL/gVS/d and 293 ± 92 mL/gVS/d, respectively) while the methane content ranged between 61 ± 7 % (AD-GAC) and 56 ± 6 % (AD-V-GAC) (Fig. S1, Table S4). Statistical treatment of the results showed that the slight differences observed between bioreactors were not statistically significant ($p > 0.05$). Analysis of VFAs content showed that the most abundant compounds were acetic and propionic acid, while butyric, isobutyric, valeric and isovaleric acids were not detected (Fig. S2a). According to the literature, acetic acid is considered the most favorable compound for methane generation, while the degradation of propionic acid is considered less beneficial [39]. The highest sum of VFAs concentrations was measured in AD-V (35 mg/L) while in the other bioreactors VFAs concentrations did not exceed 20 mg/L.

In Experimental Phase B, the application of sludge thermal pretreatment (80 °C, 1 h) did not affect the values of pH, TS and VS in influent sludge. On the other hand, the values of sCOD in influent sludge increased significantly ($p < 0.05$), from 1091 ± 403 mg/L to 4305 ± 945 mg/L (Table S4). Monitoring of the operation of the bioreactors showed that the average pH value ranged between 6.83 ± 0.13 (AD-GAC) and 6.97 ± 0.11 (AD-V), with TS concentrations ranging from 18.8 ± 3.2 mg/L in reactor AD to 29.7 ± 5.1 mg/L in AD-V-GAC (Table S4). No statistical significant differences were observed for VS removal, sCOD removal, biogas production and methane content between studied bioreactors. The average concentrations of sCOD in the effluents of each reactor were 1296 ± 573 mg/L (AD-V), 885 ± 581 mg/L (AD-V-GAC), 995 ± 646 mg/L (AD-GAC) and 1474 ± 782 mg/L. The volume of the daily biogas yield ranged between 201 ± 83 mL/gVS/d (AD) and 256 ± 101 mL/gVS/d (AD-GAC), while for the methane content the average values were 54 ± 10 % (AD-V) and 55 ± 9 % (AD-GAC) (Table S4). Comparison of the performance of the bioreactors in Experimental Phase B with that of Experimental Phase A showed that the application of thermal pretreatment improved their ability to remove sCOD and VS. Specifically, in Phase B, the mean removal of sCOD exceeded 66 % in all bioreactors (maximum mean removal of sCOD in Phase A: 51 %) (Fig. S3, Fig. S1) while higher mean VS removals were observed in all bioreactors (Table S4). However, these increased removals were not associated with increased biogas and methane production (Table S4) but with accumulation of higher concentrations of VFAs in the bioreactors. Specifically, much higher concentrations of the sum of VFAs were measured in Phase B compared to Phase A ranging between 250 mg/L (AD) to 530 mg/L (AD-V) (Fig. S2b). The predominant VFA was acetic acid while valeric acid was also detected in all bioreactors at lower concentrations. This accumulation of VFAs led to a slight drop in mean pH values, ranging from 6.83 to 6.85 in three out of four bioreactors in Phase B, compared to 7.02–7.11 in Phase A (Table S4). Previous studies have also shown that LTTP can disrupt sludge flocs and break cells walls facilitating the release of intracellular

substances and accelerating COD solubilization [12]. In regard to methane production, it has been shown that the high COD solubilization does not necessarily lead to increased methane yield, either due to the formation of refractory compounds or the solubilization of non-biodegradable organics [40].

In Experimental Phase C, the raw sludge that was used had similar TS and VS characteristics with those of previous Experimental Phases but much lower sCOD concentration (609 ± 112 mg/L comparing to 1827 ± 781 mg/L in Phase A and 1091 ± 403 mg/L in Phase B) (Table S2). The application of ultrasound pretreatment (applied power density: 1.12 W/mL, 15 min) increased the average pH values of sludge from 6.92 ± 0.09 – 7.20 ± 0.17 ($p > 0.05$) as well as sCOD concentrations from 609 ± 112 mg/L to 1809 ± 771 mg/L ($p > 0.05$). A slight increase in TS (ranging between 24.4 ± 3.3 mg/L and 25.8 ± 4.1 mg/L) and VS (ranging between 15.4 ± 2.2 mg/L and 17.2 ± 3.8) concentrations were also noticed but this was not statistically significant (Table S4). As regards the performance of the bioreactors, the average VS removal ranged between 24 ± 13 (AD-V) and 34 ± 10 (AD-V-GAC), the average sCOD removal between 49 ± 21 % (AD-V) and 62 ± 16 % (AD-GAC) and the average daily biogas yield between 99 ± 37 mL/gVS/d (AD-V-GAC) and 151 ± 44 mL/d (AD) (Table S2, Fig. S4). The differences observed between the bioreactors in the aforementioned parameters were not statistically significant. There are several potential reasons for the observed decrease in biogas yield, even though the difference was not statistically significant. First, thermal pretreatment can produce inhibitory compounds like phenols that reduce methane production. While GAC adsorbs toxic substances such as PFAS and phenols, it can also non-selectively remove essential intermediates like acetate and VFAs, limiting substrate availability for methanogens [41]. Additionally, electroactive bacteria may compete with methanogens by transferring electrons to solid surfaces or electrodes. Other possible factors include shifts in microbial community structure favoring non-methanogens, physical limitations affecting substrate diffusion, or adsorption of vital nutrients by GAC [42,43]. Determination of VFAs in the bioreactors showed that the sum of VFA concentrations ranged between 208 mg/L (AD-GAC) and 379 mg/L (AD-V) while the predominant compound was acetic acid (Fig. S2b). Excepting bioreactor AD-V, the sCOD removal observed in Experimental Phase C was higher compared to that observed in Experimental Phase A. On the other hand, the biogas and methane production in this Phase was much lower (Table S2). The increase of sCOD during ultrasound pretreatment of sludge has also been reported by other researchers [15,32]. This phenomenon is attributed to the disintegration of sludge flocs caused by hydro-mechanical shear forces and the generation of highly reactive radicals through cavitation. In previous studies, researchers suggested that an increase in sCOD following ultrasonication pretreatment would lead to a corresponding increase of methane yield [9]. However, more recent studies observed that while ultrasonication of sludge increases the solubilisation of organic compounds, it does not necessarily lead to an increase of methane production [44]. The reason for this result remains unclear. In this study, ultrasound pretreatment led to significant carbon solubilization, as evidenced by a threefold increase of sCOD. This may have caused an imbalance between hydrolysis and methanogenesis. Additionally, other factors could have also contributed to observed outcome, including the formation of compounds inhibitory to methanogens -such as ammonia or phenolic compounds- during ultrasound pretreatment, potential disruptions to the microbial community, or physical changes to the sludge that limit the accessibility of organic substrates [45,46].

3.3. Fate of PFAS in continuous-flow mesophilic anaerobic experiments

The distribution of PFAS between dissolved and solid phases was investigated in the influent and effluent samples collected during the different Experimental Phases. According to the results of all the experiments, the increase of perfluorocarbon chain length resulted in

gradual decrease of the perfluorocarboxylic acids detected in the dissolved phase (Fig. 2, Fig. S5). In Experimental Phase A, the dissolved fraction of PFPeA, which contains 5 C atoms, was higher than 76 % in all sample types, whereas for PFUdA, which contains 11 C atoms, the corresponding percentage was lower than 39 %. The presence of a sulfonic acid group in PFAS molecule resulted in a lower fraction being found in the dissolved phase, as demonstrated by the comparison between PFOS and PFOA. These are in agreement with literature where the sorption of PFOS has also been found to be greater than PFOA in sludge and soils despite both having the same number of C atoms [47,48]. The higher PFOS sorption capacity compared to PFOA is attributed to its distinct functional group with greater acidity (sulfonic acid instead of carboxylic acid), as well as the full fluorination of all eight carbons in PFOS, whereas in PFOA, only seven carbons are fluorinated, with one carbon attached to the carboxylate functional group [31]. Recently, Deligiannis et al. [28] reported similar results for sludge samples originated from thermophilic AD bioreactors.

Calculation of different PFAS mass at the influents and effluents of the bioreactors in Experimental Phase A showed that there was no removal of PFAS in the conventional AD as well in the reactor where external voltage was applied (AD-V) (Fig. 3a). On the other hand, in the bioreactors containing GAC (AD-V-GAC, AD-GAC) a partial removal of target PFAS was observed ranging up to 70 % for PFOA in AD-GAC. The removal of PFAS in this reactor was significantly higher than in bioreactors without GAC for PFPeA, PFHpA, PFOA, PFDA, PFUnA, and PFOS ($p < 0.05$). The application of 2 V of voltage in the presence of GAC did not seem to affect PFAS removal as no significant differences were observed in reactors AD-GAC and AD-V-GAC ($p > 0.05$). Comparison of the PFAS showed that lower removal efficiencies were observed for the longer perfluorocarboxylic acids, PFDA (C10) and PFUnA (C11), which are primarily sorbed to the particulate phase (Fig. 2).

In Experimental Phase B, with the exception of PFPeA, all target PFAS were partially removed in the bioreactor AD-GAC with a percentage ranging between 53 % (PFOA) to 62 % (PFHpA) (Fig. 3b). The high standard deviations values calculated in the reactors without GAC prevent drawing reliable conclusions about the ability of conventional AD and the voltage applied digester to remove PFAS. Similar to the previous Experimental Phases, a partial removal of most PFAS was also observed in bioreactors with GAC in Experimental Phase C ranging from 41 % (PFPeA) to 76 % (PFOA) (Fig. 3c). Statistical treatment of the results showed that the removal of PFAS in AD-GAC bioreactor was significantly higher than in bioreactors without GAC for PFHpA, PFOA, PFNA and PFDA ($p < 0.05$).

Regarding the role of sludge pretreatment in PFAS removal, analysis of sludge samples before and after thermal pretreatment (80 °C, 1 h) and before and after ultrasound pretreatment (1.12 W/mL, 20 kHz, 15 min) showed no changes on the total concentrations of the studied PFAS. The maintenance of concentrations at the same levels before and after thermal pretreatment can be attributed to the high thermal stability of these compounds [31]. As regards their fate during ultrasound pretreatment, the results of this study were consistent with those of Zhang et al. [32] who reported that ultrasonication at 20 kHz was ineffective to degrade perfluoroalkyl acids. According to Campbell and Hoffmann [49], the optimum frequencies for the degradation of perfluoroalkyl acids in water were 358 and 610 kHz. Additionally, Marsh et al. [50] applied high-frequency ultrasound treatment (700 kHz or 950 kHz) at power densities of 145 W/L and 90 W/L and observed high PFAS decomposition while Shende et al. [51] applied high frequency ultrasound treatment (575 kHz, 853 kHz, 1132 kHz) in water treatment and reported that more than 97 % of PFAS were degraded within 8 h. However, the aforementioned ultrasound frequencies are much higher than those commonly used for sludge pretreatment (20–100 kHz) and compared to the ultrasonication tested in the current study. Based on the above, it seems that the applied ultrasound frequency was suboptimal for PFAS breakdown. The analysis of PFAS in the dissolved and solid

Fig. 2. Percentage of PFAS detected in the dissolved phase of influents and effluents during Experimental Phase A (mean \pm standard deviation, $n = 4$). (Feed: influent; Feed (GAC): influent with addition of GAC; AD-V: anaerobic digestion with application of external voltage; AD-V-GAC: anaerobic digestion with application of external voltage and addition of GAC; AD-GAC: anaerobic digestion with addition of GAC; AD: conventional AD).

phases before and after thermal or ultrasound pretreatment showed a slight increase of the dissolved fraction after sludge pretreatment, particularly for the longer perfluorocarboxylic acids and PFOS. These differences were statistically significant for PFDA and PFUnA ($p > 0.05$) (Fig. 4).

This is the first study to investigate the fate of PFAS in mesophilic anaerobic digesters containing GAC, as well as under conditions involving a 2 V external voltage and either thermal or ultrasound sludge pretreatment. In a recent study published by our research team, Deligiannis et al. [28] operated four anaerobic digesters under thermophilic conditions for a period of 3.5 months and observed a partial decrease of total PFAS concentrations in the reactors containing GAC while their removal was negligible during conventional AD or when voltage of 0.8 V was applied. In the current study, the analysis of target PFAS in both the dissolved and particulate phase and the calculation of their total mass in the inlet and outlet of the bioreactors indicate that the possible mechanism which is responsible for their removal is biotransformation. Although the role of irreversible sorption of PFAS to GAC in the observed removal cannot be ruled out, recovery experiments of the target substances from both anaerobically digested sludge and anaerobically digested sludge containing GAC showed that there was no matrix effect for the different types of samples (Fig. S6). The biotransformation of two PFAS carboxylic acids [52], PFOA [53] and PFOS [54] under strictly anaerobic conditions has also been reported in the literature. So far, it is well-known that the addition of GAC in anaerobic digesters allows the sorption of potentially harmful substances protecting methanogens from toxicity, enhances microbial growth providing a surface for microbial biofilms to attach, and facilitates DIET between different microbial species [55,56]. Although recent studies have highlighted the beneficial role of conductive materials-enhanced DIET in the degradation of certain recalcitrant compounds under anaerobic conditions, further investigation is needed to elucidate the exact mechanisms of electron transfer between microbial species, the fate of these transferred electrons, and the interplay between sorption processes and degradation in such systems [57]. As regards PFAS, no information is available regarding the DIET effect on their removal and further research is required to understand how GAC promotes PFAS biotransformation. Identification of by-products and a fluorine mass balance is also required to fully understand the exact mechanisms of PFAS removal and confirm biotransformation [58]. Regarding the role of GAC and DIET in the degradation of other recalcitrant compounds, Azizi et al. [12] reported that GAC enhanced methane production by enriching DIET-active microbes and adsorbing polystyrene nanoplastics, which in turn reduced levels of reactive oxygen species (ROS). In another study, Lei et al. [59] reported that the addition of biochar in anaerobic membrane bioreactors

promoted the removal of recalcitrant micropollutants while biotransformation -rather than sorption- was enhanced for 13 out of 22 target compounds. This was attributed to the enrichment of microbial species involved in biotransformation.

Concerning the potential effect of thermal and ultrasound sludge pretreatment on PFAS removal during AD, comparison of the removals observed in AD-GAC bioreactor in Experimental Phases A, B, and C indicated no significant differences. Based on this, it seems that the changes on the nature of the substrate entering the bioreactor (e.g., an increase on the soluble fraction) during thermal or ultrasound sludge pretreatment do not affect the ability of microorganisms to remove these substances. Additionally, the observation that sludge pretreatment increased to some extent the dissolved fraction of long-chain PFAS without enhancing total PFAS removal underscores a key challenge in PFAS biodegradation: increased bioavailability alone does not ensure microbial degradation, particularly for highly persistent compounds such as long-chain PFAS. The reason for this observation is unclear; it does not appear to be related to microbial inhibition caused by PFAS toxicity. The concentrations of PFAS used in the current study (0.1 mg/L or 4 mg/kg TS) were lower than those reported in the literature to cause significant inhibitory effects to anaerobic microorganisms. Specifically, Jiao et al. [60] reported that the methane production during the anaerobic digestion of waste activated sludge was reduced by 4.7–18.9 % in the presence of PFOA at concentrations of 8.5 and 170 mg/kg TS, respectively. In another study, Silva et al. [61] reported that at a concentration of 0.1 mg/L, PFOA and PFOS caused less than 10 % inhibition of specific methanogenic activity in acetoclastic communities and less than 15 % in acetogenic communities, while hydrogenotrophic methanogens remained unaffected.

So far, little information is available in the literature for the effect of sludge pretreatment on organic micropollutants removal. In a recent study, Balasundaram et al. [62] applied thermal pretreatment (120–180 °C, 30–120 min) and reported higher removal of some pharmaceuticals compared to conventional AD. Taboada-Santos et al. [63] observed no difference of anaerobic biodegradability of 10 out of 12 detected micropollutants after applying thermal pretreatment at 170 °C for 20 min while Reyes-Contreras et al. [64] reported decreased concentrations in the digestate for 7 out of 9 organic microcontaminants when sequential ultrasound pretreatment (26 kHz, 200 W, 2.3–6.1 min) and thermal pretreatment (55 °C, 8 h) were applied. Alukkal et al. [24] reported a 38 % increase in fluorotelomer carboxylic acids concentration and a 26 % reduction of perfluoroalkyl carboxylic acids, after applying thermal pretreatment (165 °C, 6 bar) prior to AD.

(a)

(b)

(c)

Fig. 3. PFAS removal efficiency (mean + standard deviation, n = 4) observed in different mesophilic AD reactors during Experimental Phases A (a), B (b) and C (c). (AD-V: anaerobic digestion with application of external voltage; AD-V-GAC: anaerobic digestion with application of external voltage and addition of GAC; AD-GAC: anaerobic digestion with addition of GAC; AD: conventional AD).

Fig. 4. Percentage of PFAS detected in the dissolved phase of sludge before and after thermal pretreatment and before and after ultrasound treatment (mean ± standard deviation, n = 8).

Fig. 5. Relative abundance at the genus level at the end of Phase A in the four anaerobic bioreactors used in this study. (AD-V: anaerobic digestion with application of external voltage; AD-V-GAC: anaerobic digestion with application of external voltage and addition of GAC; AD-GAC: anaerobic digestion with addition of GAC; AD: conventional AD). For genera with unclear classification (e.g., *midas*), additional taxonomic information (e.g., family) is provided.

3.4. Microbial community analyses

To analyze the microbial profile in studied bioreactors, samples were taken at the end of Phase A. According to the results, the genus *midas_g_467*, belonging to the family *Anaerolineaceae* in the phylum *Chloroflexi*, was found in high concentrations (4.0 – 9.9 %) across the four samples (Fig. 5). This finding aligns with Wang et al. [65], who demonstrated that *Chloroflexi*, particularly from the family *Anaerolineaceae*, played a critical role in microbial network interactions under PFOS stress. Their study showed that PFOS had minimal impact on nitrogen removal efficiency in an anaerobic ammonium oxidation (anammox) system but significantly enhanced network complexity and positive interactions, with *Chloroflexi* accounting for 53.62 % of the overall microbial network. In the current study, other genera within the *Chloroflexi* phylum, such as *midas_g_944*, *midas_g_156*, *Leptolinea*, and *Longilinea*, were found in all samples with relative abundances ranging from 2.0 % to 3.5 % (Fig. 5). Ji et al. [66] highlighted the prominence of *Longilinea* in anode bacterial communities within constructed wetlands coupled with microbial fuel cells, achieving over 96 % removal efficiency for PFOA and PFOS. Genera from the phylum Synergistota, such as *midas_g_249* and *JGI-000079-D21*, were also found across all four systems in relatively high abundance (Fig. 5). Similarly, Li et al. [67] reported that *Synergistota*, although low in abundance, positively correlated with PFAS in landfill leachate, suggesting their potential role in their transformation or degradation. Kong et al. [68] observed that exposure to PFOS and polyethylene terephthalate microplastics altered bacterial community structures in thermophilic AD systems, leading to an increase in the abundance of *Synergistota* in reactors containing polyethylene terephthalate and nano zero-valent iron.

Across the four conditions in this study, similar genera were observed in all samples, though their relative abundance varied. The higher relative abundance of specific genera in reactors with GAC compared to those without may explain differences in system performance. For instance, the facultative anaerobic genus *Deftuviococcus* was exclusively identified in samples with GAC, showing a relative abundance of 3.8 – 4.0 % (Fig. 5). This observation is consistent with Senvirathna et al. [69], who reported that *Deftuviococcus* exhibited higher relative abundance (0.02 – 0.20 %) in PFAS-contaminated soils at an Australian airport, suggesting its adaptability to PFAS stress and potential role in PFAS degradation.

The facultative anaerobic bacterium *Limnobacter* was found in relative abundances of 1.3–2.8 % in samples with GAC and 0.2–0.5 % in samples without GAC (Fig. 4). Guo et al. [70] identified *Limnobacter* as a potential bioindicator of PFOA pollution due to its significant presence in PFOA-exposed microcosms and its sensitivity to PFAS exposure. Huang et al. [71] further demonstrated that PFOA exposure increased the abundance of *Limnobacter* (5.90–6.82 %) in anammox systems, attributing this increase to enhanced EPS secretion, which supported heterotrophic growth. These findings suggest that the presence of GAC in this study likely facilitates EPS secretion and biofilm formation from microorganisms, creating a favorable environment for microbial colonization and activity. This enhancement not only promotes the proliferation of adaptive microorganisms like *Limnobacter* but it is also likely to improve the system's capacity for PFAS removal, highlighting the critical role of GAC in optimizing microbial community dynamics and pollutants removal efficiency.

A higher abundance of the genus *Romboutsia*, belonging to the phylum Firmicutes, was observed in GAC systems compared to systems without GAC (Fig. 5). This study is the first to highlight the association of *Romboutsia* with PFAS presence, suggesting that its higher abundance in GAC systems may be linked to its ability to form biofilms. Chen et al. [72] identified *Romboutsia* as a dominant anaerobic bacterium in sequencing biofilm batch reactor (SBBR) systems, where its capacity to produce acetic acid through fermentation and its significant abundance under ultraviolet-irradiated conditions highlighted its adaptability and vital role in organic substance metabolism and pollutant degradation,

even under harsh environmental conditions.

A relative abundance of archaea (0.15–0.94 %) was observed for *Methanobacterium*. In contrast, *Methanothrix* exhibited increasing relative abundance across conditions, with 0.5 % in the control, 1.1 % in AD-V, 1.8 % in AD-V-GAC, and 2.6 % in AD-GAC. A similar trend was observed for *Methanomethylovorans*, which increased in systems containing GAC compared to those without. Yin et al. [73] reported a significant increase in *Methanomethylovorans* under anoxic conditions during the slow biotransformation of fluorotelomer sulfonate in wetland slurries, highlighting its potential role in PFAS adaptation and bioremediation in anaerobic environments. Similarly, Usman et al. [74] demonstrated that *Methanomethylovorans* was enriched in GAC biofilms, where it contributed to the degradation of methyl compounds in hydrothermal liquefied wastewater, enhancing methane production and organic removal. Furthermore, Na et al. [75] emphasized the resilience of *Methanomethylovorans* under stressful conditions, such as the presence of organic micropollutants, due to its ability to tolerate higher biological toxicity compared to other methanogens. These findings collectively suggest that *Methanomethylovorans* plays a crucial role in microbial adaptation and potential PFAS degradation in systems with GAC.

4. Conclusions

No statistically significant differences in the removal of VS, sCOD, biogas yield and methane content were observed between the studied bioreactors in Phase A, where raw sludge was used as feed. The mean removal of VS and sCOD reached up to 32 ± 12 % and 51 ± 19 %, respectively, biogas production up to 291 ± 82 mL/d, and methane content up to 61 ± 7 %. Thermal pretreatment of sludge at 80 °C for 1 h nearly quadrupled the concentration of sCOD in raw sludge and enhanced the ability of all bioreactors to remove sCOD and VS, achieving up to 79 ± 11 % and 52 ± 17 %, respectively, in the bioreactors containing GAC. These increased removals were not associated with increased biogas and methane production but with accumulation of higher concentrations of VFAs in the bioreactors. The use of ultrasound pretreatment at a power density of 1.12 W/mL for 15 min tripled the concentration of sCOD in raw sludge and resulted in increased sCOD removal comparing to Phase A in most of the bioreactors but did not enhance their ability to produce biogas and remove VS. PFAS removal in BMP tests ranged between 68 % (PFPeA) and 79 % (PFNA). Partial PFAS removal was also observed in all continuous-flow bioreactors containing GAC, along with a parallel increase of the abundance of PFAS-tolerant microbes. This suggests that the porous structure and high surface area may promote PFAS-targeted degradation. Future studies should focus on the role of specific microorganisms such as *Deftuviococcus*, *Limnobacter*, and *Methanomethylovorans* in PFAS fate within anaerobic digesters and explore how GAC creates a habitat that supports the proliferation of PFAS-tolerant microbes. The use of advanced analytical techniques is also suggested to identify potential transformation products in such AD reactors.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Michalis Deligiannis: Investigation. **Evdokia Gkalipidou:** Writing – original draft, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Knight Emma:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Georgia Gatidou:** Validation, Methodology. **Kostakis Marios:** Validation, Data curation. **Allan Ian:** Writing – review & editing, Validation. **Thomaidis Nikolaos:** Resources. **Gerokonstantis Dimitrios:** Software, Investigation. **Ioannis Vyrides:** Writing – original draft, Methodology. **Arvaniti Olga:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology. **Stasinakis Athanasios:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Fountoulakis Michalis:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Conceptualization.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supporting information

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found in the online version at [doi:10.1016/j.jece.2025.117933](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jece.2025.117933).

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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